

ANALYSIS ON CURE-INDUCED DEFORMATION OF FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITES USING ANISOTROPIC VISCOELASTIC MODEL

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1 Introduction

Fiber reinforced resin matrix composites have been widely used in aerospace, automobile, architecture and many other industries owing to their superior mechanical properties [1-3]. In virtue of the process-induced residual stress, which is caused mainly by the mismatch in coefficient of thermal expansion among tools, matrix and fiber, secondarily by the chemical shrinkage of thermoset resin as well as the tool-part interaction during cure, composite parts often warp when they are removed from the tools [4-8]. The distortion will adversely affect the dimensional accuracy and mechanical properties of composite parts. Hence, it is crucial to evaluate the residual stress in the design of composite parts manufacturing.

In the recent past, trial-and-error procedures were widely used to straighten the distortion, which were imprecise, costly and time-consuming in most cases. With the development of computer technology and finite element method, the finite element analysis (FEA) combined with experiments has been used as an efficient tool to estimate the evolution of the internal stress, and then to optimize the production process [9-23].

Thermoset resin cure is a complicated process during which the matrix with linear macromolecular chains transforms to a non-fusible and insoluble three-dimensional network structure through cross-linking reaction. It's definite that the residual stress and deformation are generated in this circumstance. In FEA, an applicable constitutive model for the composites is significant in order to exactly simulate the evolution of the mechanical performance of the composites. The mechanical properties of resin matrix show pronounced viscoelasticity during cure [24]. It's difficult to precisely model the viscoelastic behaviors of anisotropic resin matrix composites

when the cure advances. Furthermore, the numerical codes of viscoelastic models are rather complex, and the deficiency of computational resources should be considered as well. As a consequence, the elastic models are widely used in FEA instead [11, 13, 23]. Bogetti and Gillespie [11] applied a one-dimensional elastic model to explain the relationship between gradients of temperature and degree of cure, and then predict the residual stress and effective mechanical properties of thick-section thermoset laminates. Johnston et al. [13] presented a "cure-hardening, instantaneously linear elastic" constitutive model to analyze the five major sources of process-induced deformation identified from literatures for L-shaped laminates during autoclave process. Wang et al. [23] assumed that the material system used in their study was elastic, and on this premise, they obtained the relationship among the degree of cure, the volumetric change rate and the temperature by FEA, which provided an effective method for process optimization.

Although the elastic model is extremely mature in FEA, it is more accurate to depict the intricate thermoset composites by a viscoelastic model than by an elastic model. Consequently, more and more researches have been carried out in this field [18, 21, 25, 26]. Clifford et al. [18] used a three-dimensional anisotropic thermo-viscoelastic formulation to evaluate the dimensional stability of the V-shaped asymmetric cross-ply laminates. Li et al. [21] utilized the finite element software ABAQUS to predict the full field warpage profiles of the integrated T-shaped structures based on the thermo-viscoelastic theory. Kim and White [25] introduced a two-dimensional viscoelastic model to investigate the development of residual stress in thick composite laminates. The thermo-chemical viscoelastic constitutive equations coupled with a thermo-

chemical process model were adopted by Hwang et al. [26] to analyze the residual stress of an aluminum liner-inserted polymer composite cylinder, which was used for rocket fuselage.

In this study, both the anisotropic elastic model and the anisotropic viscoelastic model are introduced to predict the residual stress and deformation of fiber composite laminates by FEA. Thus, a comparison between them is made to analyze how the two models affect the residual stress and deformation of composite laminates in different ways. Based on the analysis, we can decide which model is the proper choice corresponding to specified conditions in FEA. In the end, the analysis on the mechanism of the residual stress and deformation is made.

2 Theoretical Models

2.1 Thermo-Chemical Model

The unsteady and nonhomogeneous temperature distribution in the composites is an important cause for residual thermal stresses, which can be obtained by coupling the transient heat transfer with the inner heat source. The three-dimensional governing equation of the Fourier's heat conduction is as follow [27]:

$$\rho_c c_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (K_{ij} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_j}) + \rho_c H_c \frac{du}{dt} \quad (i, j = 1, 2, 3) \quad (1)$$

where ρ_c and c_p are the time-dependent density and specific heat of the laminates, respectively. K_{ij} is the equivalent thermal conductivity in different directions of composites. H_c is the total heat of reaction, T is the absolute temperature, and u is the degree of cure. The needed parameters in this equation are listed in Table 1 [11, 27].

The boundary conditions are as shown below:

$$T = T(t) \quad (2)$$

$$-K \frac{\partial T}{\partial n} = 0 \quad (3)$$

where $T(t)$ is the typical temperature profile of cure cycle for the graphite/epoxy, as shown in Fig. 1. The Eq. 2 and Eq. 3 are exerted to the material surfaces and symmetric surfaces, respectively.

The initial conditions are $T(0) = T_0$ and $u(0) = 0$.

2.2 Cure Kinetic Model

An autocatalytic cure kinetic model is chosen to describe the evolution of the curing degree for

AS4/3501-6, the type of graphite/epoxy composite we choose in this study, as follows [28]:

$$\frac{du}{dt} = \begin{cases} (K_1 + K_2)(1-u)(0.47-u) & (u \leq 0.3) \\ K_3(1-u) & (0.3 < u) \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

$$K_j = A_j e^{\frac{-\Delta E_j}{RT}} \quad (j = 1, 2, 3) \quad (5)$$

where K_j is the rate constant, R the gas constant, ΔE_j the activation energy, and A_j the pre-exponential coefficient. All of the aforementioned properties for this kinetic model are presented in Table 1.

2.3 Mechanical Models

For the elastic model in this study, the relationship between stress and strain can be described by the following equation [16]:

$$\{\sigma\} = [E](\{\varepsilon^{\text{total}}\} - \{\varepsilon^{\text{tc}}\}) + \{\sigma_0\} \quad (6)$$

where $\{\sigma\}$, $\{\sigma_0\}$, $\{\varepsilon^{\text{total}}\}$, $\{\varepsilon^{\text{tc}}\}$, and $[E]$ are the internal stress, initial stress, total strain, thermo-chemical strain and elastic modulus tensor, respectively. The thermo-chemical strain $\{\varepsilon^{\text{tc}}\}$ is the simple sum of the thermal strain $\{\varepsilon^{\text{th}}\}$ and chemical strain $\{\varepsilon^{\text{c}}\}$, where $\{\varepsilon^{\text{th}}\}$ and $\{\varepsilon^{\text{c}}\}$ can be expressed as [23]:

$$\{\varepsilon^{\text{th}}\} = \{\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, 0, 0, 0\} \cdot \Delta T \quad (7)$$

$$\{\varepsilon^{\text{c}}\} = \{\varepsilon_1^{\text{c}}, \varepsilon_2^{\text{c}}, \varepsilon_3^{\text{c}}, 0, 0, 0\} \quad (8)$$

where ΔT is the temperature variation, α_i and ε_i^{c} are the thermal expansion coefficient and chemical strain in three directions of the composite, respectively. ε_i^{c} is a variable related to ε_m^{c} , which can be calculated according to the micromechanical theory [11]:

$$\varepsilon_m^{\text{c}} = \sqrt[3]{1 + \Delta u \cdot V_{\text{sh}}} - 1 \quad (9)$$

where Δu is an incremental change in the degree of cure, and V_{sh} is the total specific volume shrinkage of the completely cured resin.

A viscoelastic model is used to compare with the elastic model mentioned above in this study. Linear viscoelasticity is a commonly used approximation, where the stress linearly depends on the strain rate. The stress of the linear viscoelastic materials with thermorheologically simple behavior, such as 3501-

6 epoxy, can be calculated by the following equation [25, 29]:

$$\sigma_i(t) = \int_0^t Q_{ij}(\xi(t) - \xi'(\tau)) \frac{d}{d\tau} [\varepsilon_j^{\text{total}}(\tau) - \varepsilon_j^{\text{ic}}(\tau)] d\tau \quad (10)$$

($i, j = 1-6$)

where Q_{ij} is the cure- and time-dependent effective stiffness matrix, and τ is a dummy time-integration variable. ξ and ξ' , named reduced time, are forms of time combined with temperature and degree of cure, and can be calculated as:

$$\xi(t) = \int_0^t \frac{ds}{a_T(u_0, T(s))} \quad (11)$$

$$\xi'(\tau) = \int_0^\tau \frac{ds}{a_T(u_0, T(s))} \quad (12)$$

$$\log(a_T) = \left[-1.4 \exp\left(\frac{1}{u-1}\right) - 0.0712 \right] (T - T_f) \quad (13)$$

where a_T is the shift factor, u_0 and T_f is the reference degree of cure and temperature defined as 0.98 and 303K, respectively; s is the time integration variable.

In this study, the material is transversely isotropic in 2-3 plane. The effective stiffness matrix is expressed as [30]:

$$[Q_{ij}(t)] = \begin{bmatrix} Q_{11}(t) & Q_{12}(t) & Q_{13}(t) & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ Q_{12}(t) & Q_{22}(t) & Q_{23}(t) & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ Q_{13}(t) & Q_{23}(t) & Q_{22}(t) & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{Q_{22}(t) - Q_{23}(t)}{2} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & Q_{66}(t) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & Q_{66}(t) \end{bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

$Q_{ij}(u, \xi)$ can be signified as a form of exponential series for thermal-rheologically complex materials [25, 31]:

$$Q_{ij}(u, \xi) = Q_{ij}^\infty(u) + Q_{ij}^*(u) \sum_{m=1}^N W_m(u) \exp\left[-\frac{\xi(u, T)}{\tau_m(u)}\right] \quad (15)$$

$$Q_{ij}^*(u) = Q_{ij}^u(u) - Q_{ij}^\infty(u) \quad (16)$$

$$Q_{ij}^\infty(u) = R_p \cdot Q_{ij}^u(u) \quad (0 \leq R_p \leq 1) \quad (17)$$

where Q_{ij}^∞ and Q_{ij}^u represent the cure-dependent fully relaxed stiffness and unrelaxed stiffness,

respectively; R_p is the partition factor. When R_p is 1, the material doesn't relax, and when 0, the material fully relaxes after sufficient time. R_p is 0.14 for the material system in our study. According to the validation of experiments, Q_{ij}^∞ and Q_{ij}^u are assumed as constants for simplicity [32]. The values of Q_{ij}^u are listed in Table 2.

$$\tau_m(u) = 10^{\log(\tau_m(u_0)) + [f(u) - f(u_0) - (u - u_0) \log(\lambda_m)]} \quad (18)$$

$$f(u) = 0.0536 + 0.0615u + 0.9227u^2 \quad (19)$$

$$\lambda_m = \frac{10^{9.9}}{\tau_m(u_0)} \quad (20)$$

W_m and τ_m are the weighting factor and relaxation time of the m^{th} branched chain, respectively, which are simplified as cure-independent. The values of them are provided in Table 3 [25].

3 Model Verification

In this study, a flat plate with graphite/epoxy composite system, which is also used in the following research, is applied to validate the process. The dimensions of the uniform flat plate are 15.24 cm \times 15.24 cm \times 2.54 cm. The commercial software COMSOL Multiphysics 4.3a is applied to develop the finite element model. The constituent properties of the flat plate are listed in Table 1. The typical temperature profile of cure cycle and the comparison of results for process verification are shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2, respectively.

As depicted in Fig. 2, the curves of temperature and degree of cure calculated by this process coincide with those in references [25, 27] well within the permitted error range.

4 Results and Discussion

In this section, the laminates with the dimensions of 30 cm \times 14 cm \times 2 cm and [0/45] ply sequence are studied. The maximum deformation is indicated by the maximum absolute value of the displacement in the thickness direction (z -component) of the laminates.

4.1 Curing Parameters of Laminates

The thermal-induced strain and cure-induced strain are determined by the temperature field and degree of cure field [23]. Fig. 3 shows the evolution of the temperature and degree of cure for AS4/3501-6 at the surface point, central point of the upper layer and central point, respectively. Owing to the poor

thermal conductivity of the material, the surface point is heated fastest among the three points. In virtue of the same reason and the curing exotherm of resin, the heat in the central region of the laminates is unable to transfer to surroundings timely and induces an exothermal peak in the temperature curve of the central point. The same drift can be found in the temperature curve of the central point of the upper layer, though the exothermal peak is a bit lower. Because of the tight coupling relationship between the fields of temperature and degree of cure, the curves of the degree of cure present a corresponding trend as shown in Fig. 3(b).

4.2 Maximum Deformation of Laminates

Six control groups (including two repeated groups) with different compositions are calculated by elastic models and viscoelastic models, respectively. In this simulation, we assume that the fiber volume fraction (V_f) is 0.2, 0.5 and 0.7, respectively, when the resin curing shrinkage (V_{sh}) is 5%, as shown in Fig. 4(a). Another condition is that V_{sh} is 1%, 3% and 5%, respectively, when V_f is 0.5, as shown in Fig. 4(b). Fig. 4(a) depicts that the maximum deformation diminishes with the increase of V_f , and the gap between the two models decreases simultaneously. Due to high modulus, the carbon fiber is qualified as elastic material. With the increase of fiber content, the properties of the laminates are fiber-dominated, meanwhile, the viscoelasticity of composites is weakened gradually. What's more, the maximum deformation rises with the increase of V_{sh} and the difference between the two models increases as well. This is because that the viscoelasticity of composites is improved with the increase of V_{sh} .

4.3 Deformation Contour of Laminates

At the initial stage of cure process, the resin is viscous fluid and the stress developed in this case almost relaxes immediately [32]. As a result, there is not internal stress induced by chemical shrinkage and thermal expansion. In this study, it is assumed that the gel point is $u = 0.57$, where the thermal strain and chemical strain begin to work [24]. At nearly the time 14400s, the process begins to enter the cooling stage, at which the thermal effect plays an important role and the chemical effect almost vanishes due to curing reaction being to the end. Ultimately, the contours of the deformation which is caused by the coaction of aforementioned factors are presented in Fig. 5.

It can be seen that the laminates warp diagonally in virtue of the component of fiber. Generally, the

coefficient of thermal expansion of the matrix is considerably larger than that of fiber. In other words, the coefficient of thermal expansion of the laminates in the direction of fiber axis is much smaller than the one perpendicular to the fiber axis; meanwhile, the modulus of the composites is just the opposite. As a result, the deformation perpendicular to the fiber axis is more obvious than the one parallel to the fiber axis. The divergence mentioned above is expressed as material warpage as shown in Fig. 5. As a whole, the volumetric reduction of the laminates reveals that the chemical shrinkage of the resin and the thermal shrinkage of the laminates play more effective roles than the thermal expansion of the laminates during the cure process. Moreover, the deformation calculated by the elastic model is larger than the one by the viscoelastic model, as shown in Figs. 4 and 5. This difference is resulted from the viscoelastic stress relaxation. Essentially, the relaxed stress is consumed to overcome the friction force induced by the movement of macromolecular chain segments during cure, which should be considered in the research.

5 Conclusions

Due to the viscoelastic property of resin, the maximum deformations calculated by elastic models are larger than those by viscoelastic models. The difference between them depends on the fiber volume fraction and the curing shrinkage of resin mostly. Under the condition of the same resin curing shrinkage, if the fiber volume fraction is large enough, the difference between the two models is tiny. In this case, the elastic model can be adopted in numerical simulations so as to save the calculation time and simplify the codes. If the fiber content is the same, the increase of the resin curing shrinkage will make the simulated results reversed.

This method is also suitable for the numerical analysis on the cure-induced deformation of the other composite materials, and it may be valid to decrease the computational time and resource without reducing the accuracy.

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Table 1 Crucial thermal physical properties and cure kinetics of graphite/epoxy

Parameter	Value
ρ_c (kg/m ³)	1578
c_p (J/kg K)	862
K_{xx} (W/m K)	12.83
K_{zz} (W/m K)	0.4135
A_1 (min ⁻¹)	2.012×10^9
A_2 (min ⁻¹)	-2.014×10^9
A_3 (min ⁻¹)	1.960×10^5
E_1 (J/mol)	8.07×10^4
E_2 (J/mol)	7.78×10^4
E_3 (J/mol)	5.66×10^4
R (J/mol K)	8.31434
H_c (kJ/kg)	198.6

Table 2 Effective stiffness of AS4/3501-6

Property	Value
Q_{11} (GPa)	127.4
Q_{12} (GPa)	3.9
Q_{22} (GPa)	10.0
Q_{23} (GPa)	4.9
Q_{66} (GPa)	4.1

Table 3 Weight factor and relaxation time for AS4/3501-6 ($u = 0.98$)

m	τ_m (min)	W_m
1	29.2	0.059
2	2.92×10^3	0.066
3	1.82×10^5	0.083
4	1.10×10^7	0.112
5	2.83×10^8	0.154
6	7.94×10^9	0.262
7	1.95×10^{11}	0.184
8	3.32×10^{12}	0.049
9	4.92×10^{14}	0.025

Fig. 1. Typical temperature profile of cure cycle for the graphite/epoxy

Fig. 2. Comparisons of the results for process validation

(a) Evolution of temperature

(b) Evolution of curing degree

Fig. 3. Temperature and degree of cure histories for the graphite/epoxy laminates at different points

(a) Resin $V_{sh} = 5\%$

(b) Fiber $V_f = 0.5$

Fig. 4. Contrast of maximum deformations calculated by the two models under different conditions

(a) Elastic model

(b) Viscoelastic model

Fig. 5. Contours of the deformation calculated by the two models, when $V_f = 0.5$ and $V_{sh} = 5\%$

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